

EnvDis

D-PhD11-2.2

Responsible Partner: P23 UoS

Contributing partners: PHE

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Project deliverable	D-PhD11-2.2. End of Year 2 Progress Review
Project Acronym	PhD11-FBZ4/5- EnvDis
Author	Laura Cristina Gonzalez Villeta
Other contributors	
Due month of the report	December 2021
Actual submission month	December 2021
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R Save date: NA
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU This is the default setting. If this project deliverable should be confidential, please add justification here (may be assessed by PMT):
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input type="checkbox"/> WHO-EU <input type="checkbox"/> OIE <input type="checkbox"/> Other international stakeholder(s): Social Media: Other recipient(s):

D-PHD11-2.2

The progress review report is framed within the guidance procedures of the University of Surrey Doctoral College. It provides the opportunity to formally reflect and discuss feedback on research ideas and the extent to which they were achieved, as well as agree on a set of objectives for the months ahead.

1. Project objectives and extent to which they were fulfilled

1.1. Finalise the confirmation report, with a comprehensive literature review chapter that would resemble the one of the final thesis.

Deadline January

Done. Confirmation defended and passed on March 2021.

1.2. Identify the most relevant environmental drivers of salmonellosis and analyse conditional incidence

Deadline May-June

Partially achieved. Some relevant papers were found, which pointed us into exploring humidity and cloudiness. Conditional incidence was not possible to perform given that data were received on April. In the meantime, Laura started to get familiar with available R codes analysing other diseases and that can be quickly adapted to Salmonellosis.

1.3. Repeat objective 2 possibly discriminated by Salmonella serotype.

Deadline May-June

Dismissed. There was no serotype information in the data received. Species information is available. Enteritidis is the predominant species, so after looking at the data this objective is no longer relevant.

1.4. Perform some numerical simulations based on climate averages in the past (7, 14, and 30 days prior to the observation of a case).

Deadline February

Partially. As above, this analysis was conditional to the data, however 7 days was performed, and I am confident on how to proceed with the new data and different timelines.

Considering the delay in receiving the data, the focus was laid in learning how to code maps in R and exploring spatial distribution as well as proceeding with further literature review.

1.5. Perform a spatial analysis to look for relevant incidence differences between the 15 PHE centre-regions. probel

Deadline August 2021

Done a GIF time-lapse with the distribution of cases through the 30 years. But I am trying to improve it to be more informative.

1.6. Collect data on animal population and possibly animal disease prevalence (if available) from DEFRA, APHA and other sources. Continue contacting relevant stakeholders to investigate if there are data available on comorbidity.

Deadline August 2021

Done. Epidemiologists specialised in pig and chicken data analysis from APHA (the UK Animal and Plant Health Agency) were contacted. Small resolution animal disease is information classified to be a confidential as to be shared. As a workaround to the difficulties of getting this data sharing, we proposed a collaboration to analyse on-site the prevalence animal disease. While this solution was very well received, the lack of feedback since July makes us rule out its inclusion as part of EnvDis.

1.7. Start performing a conditional incidence analysis to investigate the likelihood of salmonellosis given environmental conditions (weather but also starting to include impact of presence of livestock/poultry in the catchment area, subject to data availability).

Deadline September 2021

Done, and good progress. The conditional analysis of weather (temperature and humidity) is almost done. Animal density distribution to follow. Analysis strictly possible until 2016 given the lack of residents information/PHE catchment area beyond this year.

On top of the goals set in the last review, I have:

- Collaborated in the publication entitled “Construction of a conceptual framework for assessment of health-related quality of life in dogs with osteoarthritis” that was recently published (24/09/2021).
- Contributed as a laboratory Research Assistant to a small research grant towards producing some experimental data on the impact of cyclic pH alterations over a Salmonella population. The title of the grant is: “Emergence of antimicrobial resistance in relation to periodicity, stochasticity and resilience of commensal microbial communities using chicken gut model as a proof of concept”. Findings from this work will be a chapter of my thesis.
- Been awarded for a short-term mission funding from the OHEJP consortium, with the aim of exchanging methodologies and results with a student working on a similar project related to Salmonella in the Netherlands with a different perspective. The objective is to validate my work as well as networking with a foreign Public Health Institution.

2. List of all training activities or workshops undertaken

Title of Training	Date:
French language classes (GGA - weekly)	07/11/20 - 28/04/21
Writing retreat - RDP	04/12/20
International Student One Health Association (ISOHA) mentorship program	11/12/20
Managing your supervisor - RDP	15/12/20
Genomics & Bioinformatics workshop – Arnoud van Vliet	14/12/20-24/12/20

Research Data Management and Open Data - Library and Learning Support Services	19/01/21
OHEJP CPD Workshop – Digital innovation for One Health practitioners	15/02/21-19/02/21
IFH Demonstrators COVID mitigation training	22/02/21
Demonstration GIS – BMS 2070 Eddie Brede	23/02/21 25/02/21 01/03/21
Demonstration ELISA – BMS 2045 K Bodman-Smith	08/03/21
OHEJP Cogwheel workshop – Versatile Emerging Infectious disease Observatory (VEO)	25/02/21
Building your professional network workshop - RDP	19/03/21
1 to 1 Career support Doctoral College – Emma Francis	24/03/21
International Women in STEM - QMUL	25/03/21
Performing Data analysis in R studio - Academic Skills and Development	26/03/21
3MT competition practice – Doctoral college	29/03/21
Networking 1 to 1 with Hanna Thompson (QMUL)	29/03/21
The Conversation media training – Doctoral college	20/04/21
Demonstration Heart dissection – BMS 2062 Vaan Der Veen	22/04/21
Demonstration Herp practical – BMS 2070 Eddie Brede	05/05/21 06/05/21
Storytelling for researchers - University of Surrey ESRC Impact Acceleration Account	10/05/21
Communication with impact - University of Surrey ESRC Impact Acceleration Account	12/05/21
Vet School Research symposium organising committee - UoS	18/03/21-02/07/21
23 Things International participant & Pod chair - RDP	08/03/21-07/06/21
Participation at the 3MTC (3-minute thesis competition) – Doctoral College	07/05/21
Participation at the 3MTC OHEJP	09/06/21
Poster presentation at the OHEJP ASM 2021	09/06/21
Participation with a lightening talk (which was awarded as best talk in its category) at the University of Surrey Veterinary Research Symposium,	01/07/21
Participant for the OHEJP Summer School	26/07/21-06/08/21

This meeting is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP.
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

Short, pre-recorded presentation – virtual ModAH2-INRA (Modelling in Animal Health series of conferences) 16/09/21

Demonstration of ante-mortem and post-mortem practical 09/12/2021

German language classes (GGA – weekly) 04/10/21- 04/05/2022

News and updates meeting with the NTD (Neglected Tropical Disease) group Biweekly